

Environmental awareness in ancient Indian philosophical thoughts: its relevance in modern society

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Environmental awareness is not a new phenomenon to understand the environment and protection of natural resources. The ancient Indian people especially the sage and the thinkers have great outlook on environmental consciousness that are reflected in their thoughts and actions. Vedas, Upanishads, Purana, and other Indian philosophical texts give a detail description of environment and also provide the basic knowledge about its importance and significance to all the living creatures. The ancient Indian Philosophy mentioned that the entire Universe consists of five gross elements- earth, water, fire, air and ether. In panchamahabhutas, the five gross elements are related to the five human cognitive organs. The nose carries an inherent relation with the earth, the tongue with the water, the eyes with the fire, the touch with the air and finally, the ear with the space. In the Vedic and Upanishadic period Yajna is considered as beneficial rituals to clean atmosphere through its medicinal smoke. But in 21st century it seems, people are reluctant to protect the environmental resources which is becoming a threat for all living beings. Now people are experiencing various environmental issues including pollution, climate change, global warming, biodiversity loss etc. In this study, an attempt is made to comprehend the level of environmental consciousness that existed in ancient India and to highlight its significance and relevance in the present-day scenario.

Keywords: Environment, Consciousness, panchamahabhutas, global warming, pollution etc.